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Annotation: *Bronchial asthma - chronic, independent, infectious-allergic is a disease caused by a contraction of the bronchial muscles shortness of breath, choking, aggressive cough and is characterized by the release of sticky sputum.*

Keywords: *Bronchial, chronic, virus, immune, blood.*

It affects children of all ages, but most children develop the disease in the first 3 years of life. Etiology. Hereditary in the development of bronchial asthma in children inclination plays an important role. Most children are family history of bronchial asthma, eczema, migraine, gout, fat and the presence of a similar disease. The environment the negative impact of factors is primarily a way of raising a child serious deficiencies in various infectious diseases, uncomfortable living conditions, leaving bad complications psychogenic effects are also important in the onset of the disease important. It is caused by exposure to various allergens sensitization is a major cause of bronchial asthma is the pathogenetic cause. Allergens are external (exogenous) and internal (endogenous), non-infectious (atopic) and infectious. Examples of non-infectious allergens are:

1. Social allergens: house dust, pillowcases, books and library dust and so on.
2. Animal and plant allergens: tree and plant dust hay, animal hair, parts of small insects, various dried foods and so on.
- 3 Some foods: eggs, strawberries, chocolate fish, etc.
- 4 Cereals: Most antibiotics, including pyrozone tools, vitamins and more.
5. Chemicals: synthetic fibers, foam, various synthetic glues, powders, etc.

These usually cause atopic bronchial asthma reasons. Examples of infectious allergens include:

1. Various bacteria, viruses, fungi and more pathogenic microorganisms
- 2.. Various helminths, simple animals and non-pathogenic microorganisms. These lead to infectious-allergic bronchial asthma produces. In addition, there are non-immunologically strained neurogenic types of bronchial asthma, which are more common in older children and are characterized by adult symptoms. appears. Clinic. The main symptom of the disease is shortness of breath and suffocation attack. In atopic bronchial asthma, such attacks may begin suddenly, often with nasal congestion and chest tightness. sensations, forced cough disturbs. In infectious-allergic bronchial asthma, it is a shortness of breath attack symptoms of rhinitis, bronchitis or pneumonia gradually begins in the form of voltage. At the onset of the disease, the child begins to feel suffocated, short of

breath, and in most cases, the process of exhalation becomes difficult and difficult breathing may also be difficult in rare cases. Breathe The output is noisy and can be heard even from a distance stands up, whistling, baby's lips bruises are a relief to children during an attack occupy a mandatory position in order to create. Hard to move, sticky, sticky during an attack sputum secretion, making it more difficult to breathe. The milder form of the disease is the less severe the attacks is characterized by the onset of the attack once a week and may pass quickly after medication or inhalation. And in the interval between attacks, children feel better, and there will be no wheezing. Infection-allergic bronchial attacks in asthma last longer, withdrawal from the attack becomes more difficult, and the child's condition even between attacks not so good - difficulty breathing, in the lungs dry wheezing is heard. In some cases, if the attack lasts 20-30 minutes or more if it does not pass in hours, if it lasts 6 hours or more, that the child has developed an asthmatic condition (status asthmaticus) is a sign. Complications. Especially when the disease lasts a long time with bronchopulmonary infection, inflammation of the nasopharynx persistent emphysema when combined with changes in the lungs atelectasis, pneumothorax, mediastinal emphysema, neurological changes in the form of physical retardation can leave complications. Consequences. Depending on many factors, the disease much better in the atopic type, the patient if the allergen is correctly identified will recover. In the infectious-allergic type, the consequence of the disease depends on the course. Nursing diagnoses. Shortness of breath, suffocation, agitation, restlessness, cough, difficulty moving sputum and child abuse from others. Additional checks. Total blood, urine, feces tests, general analysis of sputum, allergic tests, X-ray examinations of the lungs, etc. Treatment and nursing care. Bronchial asthma treatment and care were disease-free and non-invasive cycles are also carried out. In mild attacks of the disease take the child to fresh air going out, taking hot baths for feet and hands, hot soda Drinking fluids can be beneficial. Show the child pictures, read a book, telling interesting stories and distracting in other ways can also lead to an improvement in the situation. Give the child an oral bronchodilator inhalation (astmopent, salbutamol), in some cases eufillin in tablet form, ephedrine, etc. should be taken. In the absence of changes, subcutaneous solutions of ephedrine, papaverine, noshpa, any antihistamine (suprastin, dimedrol, tavegil, etc.). The nurse's main task is to carefully monitor the child's condition, calm the excitement, reassure him of the consequences of the disease, create a comfortable environment for the child, put pillows on the back or lift the head of the functional bed, open the windows, tighten clothes. lightening and providing fresh air to the room. Dilute sputum and make it easier to move for the purpose of solutan (7-10 drops each time), broncholitin (1-2 teaspoons), a teaspoon of potassium iodide (2-4% solution) spoonful of milk) to drink 2-3 times a day physiotherapy treatments are used. Sick children, at least after the last attack They are registered in the dispensary for 5 years, and at the age of 15 will be transferred to the juvenile ward of the adult clinic. Prophylaxis. Prevention of respiratory diseases, on their own timely and proper treatment, leading to a chronic appearance qto take measures not to send, on the proper growth, nutrition, physical education, physical training of the child continuous work is great in disease prevention important. He had allergic diseases and exudative diathesis special attention should be paid to children born to families.

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